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Project communication and dissemination strategy plan

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Executive Summary

This document aims at defining a common strategy for the communication and dissemination of BioSFerA project in order to reach project stakeholders and significant target groups effectively. The plan identifies project key messages, visual identity use, online and offline channels and adequate KPI to monitor performances. In the development of the document, partners have followed a bottom-up approach to harmonise all needs in joint communication and dissemination guidelines.

1. Introduction to the project

BioSFerA aims to develop cost-effective interdisciplinary technology to produce sustainable aviation and maritime fuels. Biogenic residues will be gasified, and the syngas will be fermented to produce bio-based triacylglycerides (TAGs). At the end of the project at least two barrels of Hydrotreated TAGs will be produced as next generation aviation and marine biofuels.

BioSFerA international consortium is composed by **some research and public institutes**: CETH (Greece), VTT (Finland), Fundacion Cartif (Spain), Bio base Europe pilot plant VZW (Belgium), CSIC (Spain), National Technical University of Athens (Greece); and **some private companies**: Kuwait Petroleum Research and Technology B.V. (Netherlands), RINA-Consulting spa (Italy), Sumitomo SHI FW Energia oy (Finland), GOOD FUELS (Netherlands), Environment Park spa (Italy).

1.1. Objectives

The main objective of communication and dissemination activities is to maximise the impact of BioSFerA project, reaching project stakeholders and target groups. A first analysis related to project target groups, strengths, challenges and key messages, useful for both communication and dissemination activities, is presented in *Chapter 3*. More in detail, communication channels are described in *Chapter 4* and concerned all means used to promote project progress from the beginning, targeting a multitude of audiences (not only the scientific community but the general public included). On the other hand, dissemination activities are focused on the public disclosure of the results and target actors that can learn from their disclosure (e.g., scientific community, European industry and technology provider), as shown in *Chapter 5. Table 1* summarises the difference between communication and dissemination, as it is interpreted in the document and suggested by European Commission Guidelines¹.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

Table 1 Communication and Dissemination

	What	When	To whom	How
Communication actions	Project progress	From the start of the project until the end	Stakeholders, citizens	Online and offline channels
Dissemination actions	Project results	As soon as the project produced results	Actors that can learn from the results (especially, but not exclusively scientific community and technology provider)	Online and offline channels. Especially but not exclusively: scientific magazines, scientific/thematic conferences, scientific open science repository.

2. Visual identity: logo and claim

All partners have contributed to the definition of the visual identity: logo and claim. As shown below, the official logo is directly inspired to the logo developed for the proposal submission

(Fig.1), which represents a green fuel dispenser gun drawing a circle around the earth, where an aeroplane and a boat are moving. Likewise, the two topics expressed by the new logo, represented in a different version from Fig 2 to 6, are the concept of "circular", addressed by the round shape of the earth, and "biofuel", described by the green fuel dispenser gun directly linked to a leaf. Moreover, as the old logo, also the new one keeps the icons of an aeroplane and a vessel, primary end-user of the innovative biofuel. Finally, the claim which joins the logo is "Biofuels for Biotravels", and both are reported in all documents produced within the project: deliverable, ppt presentation, communication material (flyers, roll-up, posters...). Most of the documents contain the logo displayed in Fig. 2, which is considered the official one, while the one in Fig 4 is mainly used for supports not having much space available as social media.

Figure 1 First version of BioSFerA logo

Figure 2 BioSFerA official logo

Figure 3 BioSFerA logo black and white

Figure 4 BioSFerA only logo

Figure 5 BioSFerA only logo black and white

BioSFerA

Biofuel for biotravels

Figure 6 BioSFerA claim

BioSFerA

Biofuel for biotravels

Figure 7 BioSFerA claim black and white

2.1. EU acknowledgement

All communication related to the project (including electronic communication, social media, etc...) and all infrastructures, equipment or major results funded under the grant must:

- display the EU emblem (*see Fig 8*)
- include the following text: *This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 884208. The sole responsibility for the content lies with the BioSFerA project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union*

Figure 8 EU acknowledgement

In project social media also, the EU is mentioned directly in the *profile bio* where the following sentence is reported: *This project receives funding from the @EU_H2020 Research & Innovation Programme. Any related tweets reflect only the views of the project owner.*

3. Communication and dissemination strategy management

The communication and dissemination strategy is built through a bottom-up approach where all partners are involved in making decisions. For such reason, a detailed communication and dissemination survey has circulated within the consortium after the kick-off meeting to collect first insights about partners' communication channels and internal organisation. Based on the output of the survey, a dedicated *communication and dissemination board*, composed by partner's communication manager, has been established. The main objective of the communication and dissemination board is to involve all partners in dissemination activities and decisions to increase the impact of the project results.

3.1. Target groups

The following target groups are identified as prior BioSFerA stakeholders:

1. European industry and technology providers

2. Innovation & Research Centers/Institutes
3. Policy makers
4. General public

3.2. Reaching the target groups

The strategy followed to reach all target groups and increase the impact of BioSFerA project is based on the exploitation of partners' existing networks and channels. Indeed, a large number of researchers involved in BioSFerA project are members of EU projects, EU networks (EERA, JP Bioenergy, BBI, JTI, etc.) and this is a multiplicative factor: partners will activate their networks to seek synergies, to convey interests and to increase the impact and the exploitability of the results.

TARGET GROUP 1: European industry and technology providers

How to reach:

European industry and technology providers are mainly reached during local and international events focused on BioSFerA related topics (biofuels, maritime and aviation sector). As listed in *par. 4.1*, BioSFerA consortium is planning to participate to some sectorial events where it will be possible to present the project and widen the network. Through the project social media channels and website, a thematic community is built and relevant industrial actors are engaged through a dedicated strategy and through key messages. Moreover, the final event will be specifically focused on the dissemination to possible users. Some training days may be organised for representatives of companies interested in acquiring knowledge about these technologies for future developments. These events will bring the relevant market actors together and boost the interaction and discussion between these market players. More detailed analysis of actions focused on involving this target group is described in *Chapter 6 Dissemination activities*.

TARGET GROUP 2: Innovation & Research Centers/Institutes

How to reach:

This audience is reached mainly through the participation in scientific conferences where team leaders of different WPs will present results as invited/plenary lectures. Innovation and Research Center will also be reached through the publication of scientific papers based on project results and potentially published in international journals with high impact factor. A minimum target of 10 scientific publication has been set, while some of the papers will be published after the project conclusion. Moreover, info days, training days and dedicated events will be organised in order to raise awareness on the real possibility of producing and utilise liquid fuel completely generated from by-products. More detailed analysis of actions focused on involving this target group is described in *Chapter 6 Dissemination activities*.

TARGET GROUP 3: Policy makers

How to reach:

Local policy makers (local authorities, national public bodies, international institutions) are engaged mainly through press releases where project progresses will be outlined in a non-technical language, and greater emphasis will be given to the general impact of the project instead of the innovativeness of the specific technology. Some partners may also give the possibility to visit the infrastructures involved in BioSFerA to make the results tangible. Some policy recommendations will be elaborated based on the overall results and outputs and will be used to inform policy makers about the needs and challenges of the sector (e.g. the future regulation and economic incentives).

TARGET GROUP 4: General public

How to reach:

General public is mainly reached by online channels: social media and website, which contain technical information described through an accessible language, videos and pictures. Moreover, some partners are used to send an institutional newsletter to a mailing list partially composed by general public (*see table 5*).

3.3. Strengths of the project

The communication and dissemination strategy is focused on the project's strengths, some of them listed below, that are highlighted in key messages tailored for each target group (*see par 3.5*):

1. BioSFerA responds to increasing market needs and demand for sustainable aviation and marine fuels

According to the International Air Transport Association (IATA) the request for air connectivity will continue to grow, leading to increasing demand for sustainable aviation fuels (SAF). Approximately 80 billion gallons of jet fuel, classified as kerosene-type and naphtha-type, are produced annually worldwide. The extensive use of petroleum-derived jet fuel has resulted in a remarkable decline in petroleum reserves. Furthermore, large consumption of jet fuel generates notable amounts of greenhouse gases (GHG), making the airline sector responsible for 3% of the total current GHG emissions. Therefore, in April 2018, the IMO's Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) adopted an initial strategy on the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from ships, setting out a vision to reduce GHG emissions from international shipping and, as a matter of urgency, to phase them out as soon as possible. Biofuels as BioSFerA are sulphur-free with low carbon footprint, as such, they have been identified as a technically viable solution.

2. BioSFerA addresses current policy target related to climate change and environmental protection especially in the aviation sector

The Paris Agreement's objectives related to climate change put aviation, along with other industries, under great pressure, as they are large emitters of greenhouse gases. In Europe, the pressure is growing. BioSFerA is expected to contribute to achieving European climate ambitions and targets in line with the UN Paris Agreement, the "*Clean Power for Transport: a European alternative fuels strategy*" and the European Strategy for Low-Emission Mobility. The aviation industry is committed to achieving a 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2050 compared to 2005 levels. This is why SAFs have recently started to attract great interest and have been identified by

IATA as critical to reducing CO₂ emissions in the aviation sector in combination with other innovations.

3. BioSFerA develops a cost-effective and versatile value chain with favourable conditions for profitable investments around Europe

BioSFerA will produce a biofuel which is developed following a Full Value Chain Pilot Evaluation, where all relevant actors are represented in the consortium, guaranteeing the validation of the integrated process at a relevant scale.

4. Environmental and economic costs reduction

BioSFerA is expected to reduce costs and improve performances of renewable fuels for aviation and shipping. The proposed concept offers several advantages that can achieve significant improvements in the field of advanced biofuels production with respect to efficiency enhancement, decreasing in production costs, reduction of the environmental impact and overall increase of benefits for the society. Indicatively, some of the set targets are: 1) reduction of production costs compared to other technologies: 26 – 60%, 2) Improvement in biomass conversion efficiency >28% compared to the most efficient state-of-the-art technology, 3) at least 22% reduction of land use compared to other biofuel technologies

5. A next-generation drop-in biofuel

BioSFerA will develop next-generation high quality non-food/feed drop-in biofuel and alternative renewable fuel technology for aviation and shipping, which substantially evolves beyond the state-of-the-art performance regarding conversion efficiency, cost and feedstock supply. This kind of biofuels are considered as "next-generation drop-in biofuels" as none of the already existing technologies (FT, HEFA, SIP, ATJ, etc.) is applied on a large scale and the synergies of thermochemical and biochemical pathways are innovatively exploited. Moreover, the project includes several innovations, with potential for commercial and academic exploitation, including:

1. The design of a novel process platform for biofuels blends production, enabling the combination of valuable chemical building blocks production and the valorisation of by-products.
2. Integration of biological, chemical and fossils resource-based process for long-chain biohydrocarbons production
3. Biotechnological process and products, including selected yeast strains for bioconversion of industrial interest
4. A sustainable and green-catalyst based process for the chemical conversion
5. Pilot and scalable process that can be applied to chemicals production with other applications different from fuel for production

Application of new biofuels completely generated from renewable sources to the aviation and shipping sectors that have not yet been penetrated by eco-solutions in an effective operative manner. BioSFerA, other than reduce GHG emissions, will also provide a tangible example for the whole sector as first application of alternative propulsion, especially for the aviation sector.

6. Sustainable solution for biogenic residues energy exploitation

Thanks to the Dual Fluidised Bed Gasification technology (DFBG) developed by VTT, the process can be driven feedstock-flexible using a broad and variable portfolio of biogenic residues which do not come in conflict with food production and tend to avoid land use restrictions. Therefore, within BioSFerA, biomass feedstock from all biogenic residues categories (i.e. forest, agricultural and industrial residues as well biogenic residues from wastes) will be examined. Moreover, the feedstock types were wisely selected aiming to represent sustainable supply chain scenarios from various regions in Europe.

3.4. Challenges

BioSFerA communication and dissemination activities also have to face some peculiar challenges that have to be adequately tackled and anticipated. Here below, some of the possible threats.

- The participation and the organisation of networking events and conferences is threatened by COVID 19 outbreak and by the strict prevention measures (travel restrictions and social distancing).
- BioSFerA addresses multidisciplinary scientific domain, therefore it is not easy to identify the correct audience that fully understands the innovative potential of the project.
- Because of the scientific complexity and academic level needed to understand the project it is challenging to communicate through more “divulgative channels” targeting final consumers and general public.

3.5. Key messages

Table 2 BioSFerA key messages

Stakeholder group	Representatives examples	Key messages
European industry and technology providers	Technology providers Feedstock suppliers Refineries Fuel traders Final end-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainability and market potential of BioSFerA biobased fuels - BioSFerA innovative process is validated in industrially relevant environment scale - BioSFerA is definitely considered as "next-generation drop-in biofuels" completely generated from by-products - A great variety of biogenic residues that can be used as potential feedstock - BioSFerA quality comparable to commercial HVO
Innovation Research Centers/Institutes	& Researchers, networks of partner organisations, biobased scientific platforms, universities	BioSFerA produces relevant innovations both from an academic and commercial perspective (see " <i>An innovative next-generation drop-in biofuels</i> ", par 3.5)
Policy makers	Regional/local authorities and public administration, EU national and regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -BioSFerA addresses current policy target related to climate change and environmental protection especially in aviation sector -Policy makers should acknowledge the importance of the implementation of dedicated measures to boost innovation in

	governmental bodies	the biofuels sector, addressing its needs and challenges (<i>e.g. regulation and economic incentives</i>). -BioSFerA is compliant with REDII annex IX
General public	Citizen at large Civil society	- BioSFerA aims at reducing the environmental impact generated by aviation and maritime sector, giving its contribution in tackling climate change threats. -Use of microbes for production of fuels

4. Communication channels

4.1. Digital media

4.1.1. Websites

A project website is created following BioSFerA visual identity (logo, mood, colours), as shown in *Fig 9*. The website contains 5 sections (Project, Consortium, Publication and news, Contact, project repository) which are regularly updated with news available for partners to translate. In addition to the institutional website, partners website are used as well to amplify the impact of the dissemination activities. Below, in *Table 3*, are the partners' website and the estimated monthly visitors.

Figure 9 Project home page (draft version)

Table 3 BioSFerA partners' website

Partner name	Partner website	Website visitors/month
CERTH	https://www.certh.gr	2500
CERTH	https://www.cperi.certh.gr/projects-activities/	N/A
VTT	https://www.vttresearch.com/en	N/A
CARTIF	https://www.cartif.es/	500
BBEPP	http://www.bbeu.org/pilotplant/	N/A
CSIC	https://www.cib.csic.es/es/	3.4915
KPRT	https://www.q8research.com/	N/A
	https://www.q8.it	300.000 – 600.000
	https://www.okq8.se	400.000
	https://www.okq8.dk	50.000 – 100.000
	https://www.q8.be	N/A
	https://www.q8aviation.com	N/A
RINA-C	https://www.rina.org/en/	150 K
SFW	https://www.shi-fw.com/	N/A
GOOD FUELS (GF)	https://goodfuels.com/	1,3 K (English website) – 310 (Dutch website)
NTUA	https://www.ntua.gr/en/	N/A
ENVIPARK	https://www.envipark.com/	1500

4.1.2. Social media

Social media are considered one of the most useful measures to disseminate projects updates and results, therefore is created a dedicated BioSFerA Twitter and LinkedIn profile. In addition to the institutional project profiles, partner social media are used as a multiplier of BioSFerA dissemination activities, as shown in *Table 4*. Moreover, In the table below, some partners have indicated the availability of their own channels to repost BioSFerA contents.

Table 4 Social media accounts

Partner name	Social media profile	Social media profile followers
TWITTER		
PROJECT ACCOUNT	@BioSFerA Project	N/A
CERTH (2-3 posts/year)	@CERTHellas	1832
VTT	@VTTFinland	20.300
CARTIF (3/month)	@CARTIFCT	2.850
BBEPP	@BioBaseEuropePP	1.199
CSIC (8/month)	@CIB_CSIC	2.496
KPRT		
	@OKQ8	7.735
	@Q8	17.497
	@Q8 Kuwait Petroleum Italia S.p.A	18.301
RINA-C (2/week)	@RINA1861	1.795
SFW	@SumitomoSHIFW	103
GOOD FUELS (GF)	@GoodFuelsmarine	753
NTUA		N/A
ENVIPARK (4/month)	@EnvironmentPark	479
LINKEDIN		
PROJECT ACCOUNT	@BioSFerA (tbc)	N/A
CERTH		N/A
VTT	@VTT	31.462
CARTIF (1/month)	@CARTIF	4.936

BBEPP	@Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant	3.831
CSIC	N/A	
KPRT	@Kuwait Petroleum Research and Technology	N/A
RINA-C (6/year)	@RINA	139.215
SFW	@Sumitomo SHI FW	3.300
GOOD FUELS (GF)	@Good fuels	2.094
NTUA	@NTUA	3.460
ENVIPARK (4/month)	@ENVIPARK	2.380

The WP8 responsible partner manages BioSFerA social media profiles and regularly involve partners communication managers to re-post and provide contributes to the editorial plan. The contents shared in project social media are in English.

To differentiate the type of contents shared and fully benefit from the social media potential, some of the rules followed for the content strategy and social media management are listed below:

- Use meaningful # in order to be in the flow of the BioSFerA topic related conversations. Some ideas (#Biofuels, #Biotravels, #energy transition, #aviation, #maritime, #research, #energy).
- Report the claim of the project "Biofuels for Biotravels!" to make them consistent with the whole communication strategy.
- Tag and connect with EU institutions², other EU-funded projects and notify the Project Officer of upcoming publications to maximise their visibility.
- Try to engage the audience asking questions or using replies, retweets or tags.
- Follow an editorial strategy based on different types of contents and diverse sources (text, pictures, videos, polls, links, etc.), for example:

² https://europa.eu/european-union/contact/social-networks_en#

1. Posts related to BioSFerA updates and news (presentation of partners, news about the publication of papers concerning project results, release of relevant project output, project progresses)
2. Share for share of interesting insights related to project topics (research results and new technologies, relevant infographics)
3. Live posting during project events or when participating in thematic Conferences/Fairs

Twitter and LinkedIn profiles are updated regularly with at least two posts every week, following an editorial plan shared with all consortium in advance. The social media strategy as well as the editorial plan is adapted to specific needs and requests that may arise during the project.

4.2. Newsletters and Traditional media

After each project meeting (every six months) the WP 8 leader realise a synthetic text concerning the project most relevant progress and accomplishments which is published on BioSFera website; partners have 15 days before the publication to notify their amendments. Partners are invited to translate the text and use their own channels (websites, newsletter and press office) to disseminate the news giving 1 week to the consortium if they want to make significant modifications. *Table 5* shows partners who regularly send newsletters, the number of subscribers and the ones who have a press office.

Table 5 BioSFerA partners institutional newsletter

Partner name	URL for subscription	Subscribers	Target group	Press office
CERTH	NA			
VTT				No (but contacts with the press)
CARTIF				Yes
BBEPP				No

CSIC	https://www.cib.csic.es/outreach	400	General public and scientific community	No
KPRT		N/A	an internal corporate newsletter distributed to the complete holding of Kuwait Petroleum (KPC, KNPC, KPI, OKQ8.....)	No
RINA-C		N/A		TBD
SFW	N/A			
GOOD FUELS (GF)				Yes
NTUA	Institutional channels are not available for research projects dissemination purposes			
ENVIPARK	https://www.envipark.com/chisiamo/newsletter/	1500	General public	Yes
ENVIPARK	CLEVER members only	800	SMEs belonging to CLEVER, cleantech, regional cluster	Yes

5. Dissemination activities

This section is aligned with Article 29 — Dissemination Of Results — Open Access — Visibility of EU funding, cited in the BioSFerA Grant Agreement:

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means

(other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

As mentioned above, dissemination activities are focused on results and target actors that can learn from their disclosure.

5.1. Dissemination channels

5.1.1. Academic publications

Partners belonging to Research and public institution will publish papers based on project results and potentially published in international journals with high impact factor. A minimum target of 10 scientific publication has been set, while some of the papers will be published after the project conclusion.

The academic dissemination will be coordinated by CERTH and ENVIPARK. The content will be reviewed by the consortium's Scientific Committee (SC). The specified conditions for publication must be applied to the following formats: journal papers, book chapter, conference proceedings and peer-review publications. The scientific journals listed below have been identified as potential targets for academic dissemination:

Table 6 Potential journals for academic dissemination

Journal name	Publisher	Impact factor	ISSN	Areas of research
Applied Energy	Elsevier	8.848	0306-2619	energy conversion and conservation, optimal use of energy resources, energy processes analysis and optimization, mitigation of environmental pollutants, sustainable energy systems.
Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology	Wiley	2.75	1097-4660	chemical, technology, biotechnology, catalysis, biocatalysis, environment, fermentation,
Fuel	Elsevier	5.578	0016-2361	Energy sources linked with environmental aspects and pollution
Fuel processing technology	Elsevier	4.982	0378-3820	Scientific and technological aspects of converting fossil and renewable resources to clean fuels, value-added chemicals, etc; renewable energy and storage energy, production of non-carbon-containing fuels, as hydrogen and ammonia
ChemSusChem	Chemistry Europe	7.962	1864-564X	Research about chemistry and sustainability, material science, chemical engineering and biotechnology
Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	Elsevier	12.110	1364-0321	Renewable and sustainable energy such as bioresources, geothermal, hydrogen, etc.; give solution and support for the transition to low carbon future;
Energy and Environmental Science	Royal Society of Chemistry	30.289	1754-5706	Biochemical and biophysical science and chemical and mechanical engineering, energy conversion and storage
Biomass conversion and Biorefinery	Springer	2.602	2190-6815	Thermo-chemical, physico-chemical and bio-chemical conversion including preparation of

				biomass to produce energy and chemical products. Bioengineering, renewable Energy and Environmental Protection
International Journal of Energy Research	Wiley	3.741	1099-114X	Energy management, production, conversion, conservation, systems, technologies, applications and environmental impact.
Applied microbiology and biotechnology	Springer	3.530	0175-7598	Prokaryotic, eukaryotic cells, relevant enzymes and proteins; applied genetics and molecular biotechnology; genomics, proteomics.
Microbial Cell Factories	Springer	4.400	1475-2859	Microbial cells as producers of recombinant proteins and natural products, or as catalyzers of biological transformations
Bioresource Technology	Elsevier	7.539	0960-8524	Biomass, biological waste treatment, bioenergy, biotransformation, bioresource systems analysis, biofuels and thermochemical conversion of biomass

In case an author publishes an academic publication about the BioSFerA results and methodologies outside of the rules of the project, the lead partner can adopt measures from the removal of authorship to contact the publishing entity/ journal to correct or remove the publication

5.1.2. Open Access

As stated in the Grant Agreement, article 29.2 Open access to scientific publications, *“Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results”*.

The Grant Agreement article 29.3 on Open access to research data *and the Data management Plan (deliverable 1.2)*, specifies the regulation for the publishing of data collected during the project. To accomplish these obligations, both “green” and “gold” open access routes will be adopted. “Green” open access (also referred to as self-archiving), is the upload of a final peer

reviewed manuscript through an online repository. This may be possible after an embargo period set by the publisher. On the other hand, “gold” open access enables the article to be freely and permanently accessible for everyone, immediately after publication.

CERTH, as the project coordinator, is committed to guaranteeing that the project results will be readily accessible. For that reason, CERTH suggests to host all the scientific publications related to BioSFerA project in online research dissemination platforms such as OpenAIRE’s Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>) and ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net/>). The bibliographic metadata as well as the relevant links to the repository platforms will be also exposed at the BioSFerA website (<https://biosfera-project.eu/>).

Regarding gold open access route, a part of some partners’ budget is foreseen to be used for the coverage of the publication fees of such manuscripts.

5.1.3. Events

As already mentioned, physical or virtual events (depending on COVID 19 restrictions), are useful means to disseminate and widen the project network. Below are examples of relevant international events which take place on a regular/annual basis and could be used for disseminating BioSFerA progress and results. ENVIPARK updates the academic and non-academic events list in the shared drive and ensures that both Scientific Publication and dissemination record is updated. For this kind of events, partners agree to share fifteen days in advance the materials presented during non-scientific conference.

Table 7 International events related to BioSFerA topics

Planned/actual date	Type	Partner responsible/involved
Pollutec Fair (Lyon-France)	Fair	ENVPA
Genova International Boat Show	Fair	RINA-C
Ecomondo (Rimini -Italy, November 2020)	Fair	ENVPA
European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	Conference	CERTH
ECOS International Conference	Conference	CERTH
20th European Congress on Biotechnology (ECB) (Maastricht-Netherlands, 9-12 May 2021)	Conference	CARTIF, CSIC, BBEP

9th Congress of European Microbiologists (Hamburg-Germany, 12-14 July 2021) ONLINE	Conference	CARTIF, CSIC
4th Edition Aportando valor al CO2 (Spain 2021)	Fair	CARTIF
BIOTEC 2021 (Spain)	Conference	CSIC, CARTIF
21th European Congress on Biotechnology ECB (EFB) (2022)	Conference	CSIC
Word Bio Markets	Fair	GF
Biofuels International	Conference	GF, KPRT
Oleofuels	Conference	GF, KPRT
Green4Sea Conference (Athens, 2021)	Conference	NTUA, CERTH
SMM Fair (Hamburg, Q3 2022)	Fair	NTUA
Posidonia Shipping Exhibition	Fair	NTUA, CERTH
Bio World Congress on Industrial Biotechnology and AgTech (North Carolina)	Conference	BBEPP
International Conference on Renewable Resources & Biorefineries (Toulouse, June 2021)	Conference	BBEPP
C1NET conference (UK, January)	Conference	BBEPP
EFIB 2020 (Brussels, BE, October 2020)	Conference	BBEPP
KOGS expo (Kuwait, October 2021)	Fair	KPRT
Final BioSFerA Conference (Turin – Italy, M47)	Conference	ALL

5.1.4. Use of BioSFerA research in teaching

Partners are encouraged to use BioSFerA project to support academic teaching. Examples of use include:

- Using the BioSFerA project as examples within lectures
- Using BioSFerA as a focus of Masters and PhD theses

5.2. Funding statement

The first author must ensure the in every publication:

- display the EU emblem
- include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 884208. The sole responsibility for the content lies with the BioSFerA project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union

6. Gender equity

BioSFerA partners are committed to foster gender equality in accordance to Articles 2&3 of the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) and other EU policy directives (COM (96) 67 final) and reports (EUR 20022). Also, the BioSFerA consortium will fully support the EU ambitions and policy on the issue of gender equality stated in the EC papers "*Women and Science, Mobilising women to enrich European Research*" and "*Women and Science: the gender dimension as leverage for reforming science*". This commitment is taken into high consideration also in communication and dissemination activities. In fact, partners:

- Make sure that the images chosen for communication and dissemination materials do not reinforce gender stereotypes and are representative of a wide mix of people belonging to different contexts and background.
- Ensure that the language used actively promotes gender equality

7. Evaluation and monitoring of communications and dissemination activities

WP 8 leader monitor and report continuously about communication and dissemination activities, while all partners indicate specific initiatives undertaken to track them. To benchmark impacts and results, here below are listed some hypothetic targets that may be adjusted and readapted in the first 24 months.

Traditional media

- 11 articles in traditional media (one each partner)
- 10 scientific publications

Social media statistics:

- 300 Twitter and LinkedIn followers

- 250 Tweets
- 120 LinkedIn posts

Website statistics

- 400 visits per month (average)

8. Exchanges with other projects

To increase project visibility and its impact BioSferA consortium has identified some research projects to be linked with (*see TABLE 22*): inviting them in relevant BioSferA events, following their profiles on social media to create synergies and strengthen the community.

Table 7 Research projects to be linked with

Project name	Relation to BioSferA
Gasification	
FLEXCHX	(H2020) Deals with the development of integrated hybrid process combining electrolysis and gasification. The produced hybrid gas is further processed to FT-wax and upgraded by oil refining equipment. [VTT]
COMSYN	(H2020) This project focuses on the production of transportation liquids (FT products) in the scale of 50-150 MW (fuel input), based on steam-blown dual fluidised-bed gasification of biomass residues. [VTT]
NEXTUCG	(Industrial demonstration project funded by Neste Oil and Stora Enso Oy) This project focused on the development of technologies and engineering solutions for a commercial-scale BtL plant. [VTT]
BTL2030	(National) Transport fuels production (especially FT-diesel and SNG) at a scale of 100-150 MW based on dual-fluidised-bed gasification followed by filtration and reforming. [VTT]
BiGPower	(FP6). High-efficiency power production by advanced gasification technologies. [VTT, CERTH]
FLEDGED	(H2020) This project combines a flexible Sorption Enhanced Gasification (SEG) process and a novel Sorption Enhanced DME Synthesis (SEDMES) process to produce DME from biomass with an efficient and low cost process. [SFW, CSIC]

CLARA	(H2020-RES21 2018) Develop a concept for the production of road biofuels based on chemical looping gasification of biogenic residues. [CERTH, CSIC]
Waste & Biomass valorisation	
LIFE BIOMASS C+	(LIFE) This project aims to demonstrate improvements in climate mitigation strategies through the production of sustainable biofuel. [CERTH, CARTIF]
REHAP	(H2020) This project aims to strengthen the European bio-economy industry by creating novel materials from agricultural and forestry waste, and considering how they can be used commercially in the green building sector. [CARTIF, VTT, RINA-C]
LIFE VALPORC	(LIFE) This project demonstrates a sustainable alternative to the management of pig carcasses and manure, focusing on the environmental problems derived from its current management and valorising these wastes by transforming them into biofuels (biogas and biodiesel) and organic fertilisers. [CARTIF]
BAMBOO	(H2020) This project is developing new technologies for energy and resource efficiency challenges in four intensive industries. [CERTH, RINA-C]
MUSIC	(H2020) This project aims to facilitate further market uptake of three types of IBC (pyrolysis oil, torrefied biomass and microbial oil) by developing feedstock mobilisation strategies, improving logistics and development of IBC trade centres. [CERTH, GF]
Fermentation / Biochemical conversion	
Carbosurf	(BBI/H2020) This project aims to develop new biobased processes as well as products and solves bottlenecks in the fermentative production of biobased biosurfactants and specialty carbohydrates. [BBEPP]
BIOCONCO2	(H2020) Develops and validates a platform of flexible and versatile techniques capable of using biological processes to transform raw CO ₂ from various industries into value-added chemicals and plastics. [BBEPP]
LIAR	(H2020) This project aims to develop a next-generation, selectively-programmable bioreactor. [CSIC]
CELBICON	(H2020) This project aims at the development of new CO ₂ -to-chemicals technologies, conjugating at once small-scale for an effective decentralised market penetration, high efficiency/yield, low cost, robustness, moderate operating temperatures and low maintenance costs. [CSIC]
IBISBA 1.0	(H2020) The overarching aim of this project is to support and accelerate the uptake of industrial biotechnology as a key enabling technology for advanced manufacturing. [CSIC, VTT, NTUA]

WoodZymes	(BBI/H2020) Entire value chain from forest biomass to phenolic and sugar-derived equivalents of fossil-derived chemicals for the manufacture of medium-density fibreboard (MDF), polyurethane (PU) insulation foam and bleached paper. [CSIC]
ENGICOIN	(H2020) Development, of new microbial factories (MFs), integrated in an organic waste anaerobic digestion (AD) platform, based on engineered strains exploiting CO2 sources and renewable solar radiation or H2 for the production of value-added chemicals. [ENVPA]
HY-TIME	(FP7) Delivers a bioprocess for decentral H2 production from 2nd generation biomass using thermophilic bacteria which have shown superior yields in H2 production from biomass. [ENVPA]
MOTOR	(TKI Biobased Economy) the project aims to produce biofuels from paperpulp, through IBE fermentation and enzymatic condensation to long chain alcohols, that will be hydrotreated to iso and n-paraffins [GF, KPRT]
Biofuel production	
LIFE BIOSEVILLE	(LIFE) Develops an integrated and sustainable system for the recovery of used frying oils generated in the city of Seville in order to produce a new biofuel, more competitive and efficient, consisting of methyl esters and glycerine ethers. [CARTIF]
2GBiofuels	(National-FN) Pilot-scale development of new 2G BTL technologies based on gasification & pyrolysis. [SFW, VTT]
NextGenRoadFuels	(H2020) Develops a competitive European technology platform for sustainable liquid fuel production. [CERTH, GF]
ToSynFuel	(H2020) Builds-up, and demonstrates the Synthetic Fuels and Green H2 production from organic waste biomass, mainly sewage sludge. [GF]
Renewell	(National- NL) Development of a catalytic hydrotreatment process for the production of drop-in biofuels. [GF]
BIOMETHAIR	(National-IT) Develops and integrates a number of advanced technologies able to offer a comprehensive approach for self produced automotive biofuel completely derived from biomass. [ENVPA]

9. Communications products

- Website: <https://biosfera-project.eu/>
- Project logo: logo and claim and only logo, coloured and black and white
- Claim graphic (Biofuels for Biotravels!)
- Project scheme: to be used both for the website and in communication materials (see Fig.10)

- Word template for reports
- PowerPoint template for presentations
- Flyer template
- Poster template (PPT and InDesign)
- Roll-up banner

Figure 10 BioSFerA project scheme

10. Translations and printing

Envipark provides all communications materials and products (see above) in English only. It is the responsibility of partners to ensure relevant materials are translated, printed and used for the project locally.

11. Annex 1: Consent form

I, _____ (name in print), give my permission for partner' name on behalf of BioSFseraA project, to videotape, audiotape, photograph, record, edit or otherwise reproduce my voice, image or likeness, and to use it in various formats and for the purposes within BioSFseraA's aims of knowledge transfer, publicity and awareness raising.

Distribution methods may include, but are not limited to, television (including UCTV, broadcast, cable, and satellite), the internet (including webcasts and podcasts), print publications or any other medium now existing or later created.

BioSFerA retains the right not to use the footage for other than archival purposes. Any copyright-protected works which I deliberately provide or otherwise include as part of this recording are either my own property or works for which I have the permission of the copyright owner to use in this way.

I hereby release, waive and discharge partner' name and its officers, agents, and employees and other BioSFerA partners from any and all demands, claims, causes of action, damages and liabilities directly or indirectly arising out of any use of my name, affiliation, data and other information, image, or voice pursuant to the foregoing grant of rights as indicated further above.

Signature: _____

Place: _____

Date: _____

Name of BioSferA witness (in print): _____

Position/Institution: _____

Signature: _____

Place: _____

Date: _____

12. Annex 2: Academic and non-scientific dissemination formats

ACADEMIC PROPOSAL FORMAT
Responsible for submission (name and institution)
Date (date of submission for review)
Enlist all authors
Thematic area (scientific field)
Conference information (Please insert complete name, place, dates, organiser, track in which you intend to participate, deadline for the abstract submission)
Abstract title
Abstract (Please insert complete text for submission)
Evidence of participation (website news, conference pictures, Agenda...)

NON-ACADEMIC PROPOSAL FORMAT
Responsible for submission (name and institution)
Thematic area (Conference/event topic)
Conference information (Please insert complete name, place, dates, organiser, track in which you intend to participate, deadline for the abstract submission)
Title of the intervention
Evidence of participation (website news, conference pictures, Agenda...)